

Synthesis and characterization of the first mononuclear glycolate-aryloxide derivatives of antimony(III)

Sunita Goyal^a and Anirudh Singh^{b*}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Jaipur Engineering College, Kukas, Jaipur-303 101, Rajasthan, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004, Rajasthan, India

Manuscript received 01 April 2013, accepted 08 May 2013

Abstract : Equimolar reactions of $\overline{\text{OGOSbOPr}}^i$ with ArOH (substituted phenols) in benzene after usual work-up afford hydrocarbon soluble, monomeric derivatives of the type $\overline{\text{OGOSbOAr}}$, where $\text{G} = \text{CHMeCH}_2\text{CMe}_2$: $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Me}_{2-2,6}$ (1), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}^i\text{-2-Me-5}$ (2), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}^i\text{-2,6}$ (3) and $\text{G} = \text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2$: $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Me}_{2-2,6}$ (4), $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}^i\text{-2,6}$ (5). The derivative (1) has also been prepared by *in situ* by equimolar reaction of $\text{Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$, $\text{HOCHMeCH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{OH}$ and $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Me}_{2-2,6}$ in refluxing benzene. All of these new derivatives have been characterized by elemental analyses, molecular weight measurements and spectroscopic (IR and ^1H NMR) studies.

Keywords : Antimony(III), glycolates, aryloxides, spectroscopy.

Introduction

The metal-aryloxide bond is one of the most prominent component of rapidly increasing number of inorganic and organometallic derivatives^{1,2} and is also present in nature in a large number of metalloproteins³. The chemistry of metal-aryloxides² and -glycolates^{4,5} has grown steadily over the last five decades. The X-ray crystallographic structural elucidation of $\text{Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ ⁶ and $\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Me}_{2-2,6})_3$ ⁷ depict dimeric structure for the former involving isopropoxo bridging in tetrahedral environment of isopropoxo groups around antimony, whereas later is a three coordinate monomer due to steric reasons, adopting a trigonal pyramidal architecture capped by a stereochemically active lone electron pair. Interestingly, analogous derivative derived from sterically compact methoxy groups forms a layer structure incorporating SbO_6 moieties⁸, where the coordination number at antimony is six. The antimony ethylene glycolate-acetate complex $[\text{Sb}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_4\text{O})(\text{OAc})]$, which exhibits polycondensation catalytic activity is shown by X-ray diffraction studies⁹ to consist of a one-dimensional chain in which the oxygen atoms of the glycolate moiety of each $[\text{Sb}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})(\text{OAc})]$ fragment bridge to the antimony centers of two

adjacent fragments, $[\text{Sb}(\eta^2\text{-OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O})(\text{OAc})]_n$. Reactions of $\text{Sb}(\text{OEt})_3$ and glycols in different molar ratios were investigated¹⁰ as early as in 1965, followed by synthesis of another type of mixed-ligand derivatives of antimony containing glycolate and a bidentate moiety with phenoxo functionality¹¹. Reactions of SbCl_3 with alkali metal (Na or K) aryloxides in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios afford antimony aryloxide-chloride derivatives, which are reported¹² to be monomeric in refluxing benzene. It is worth mentioning that many of the antimony ethoxide-glycolate derivatives¹⁰ are either insoluble or poorly soluble even in hot benzene, except the derivatives derived from hexylene glycol or pinacol, which are sufficiently soluble.

In view of the above and our continuing interest in mixed-ligand derivatives of group 15 elements^{11,13}, it was considered to be worthwhile to investigate the possibility of isolating hydrocarbon soluble and monomeric antimony(III) glycolate-aryloxide derivatives, which were not known prior to the present studies. We, therefore, report in this paper for the first time the synthesis, spectral (IR and ^1H NMR) properties, and ebullioscopic molecular weight measurements of five derivatives of the type $\overline{\text{OGOSbOAr}}$ (where OGO is a glycolate group and

*Present Address : M-2/213, Sector-H, L.D.A. Colony, Kanpur Road, Lucknow-226 012, Uttar Pradesh, India.

OAr represents an aryloxy moiety).

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Equimolar reactions of $\overline{\text{OGOSbOPr}^i}$ with substituted phenols (abbreviated as ArOH) in benzene afford mixed, glycolate-aryloxy derivatives of antimony(III) according to the following reaction :

(1) : G = CHMeCH₂CMe₂, Ar = C₆H₃Me₂-2,6

(2) : G = CHMeCH₂CMe₂, Ar = C₆H₃Prⁱ-2-Me-5

(3) : G = CHMeCH₂CMe₂, Ar = C₆H₃Prⁱ-2,6

(4) : G = CMe₂(CH₂)₂CMe₂, Ar = C₆H₃Me₂-2,6

(5) : G = CMe₂(CH₂)₂CMe₂, Ar = C₆H₃Prⁱ-2,6

The derivative (1) has also been prepared *in situ* by equimolar reactions of Sb(OPrⁱ)₃, HOCHMeCH₂CMe₂OH and HOC₆H₃Me₂-2,6 under refluxing conditions in benzene :

All these derivatives (Table 1) are highly moisture-sensitive colourless to pale yellow solids, soluble in common

Table 1. Analytical and some physical data for the compounds (1)-(5)

Compd. Empirical formula	Colour and state	Analysis (%) :			Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)
		C	H	Sb	
(1) C ₁₄ H ₂₁ SbO ₃	White solid	46.78 (46.81)	5.84 (5.89)	33.85 (33.91)	350 (359)
(2) C ₁₆ H ₂₅ SbO ₃	White solid	49.52 (49.64)	6.45 (6.51)	31.38 (31.45)	382 (387)
(3) C ₁₈ H ₂₉ SbO ₃	Pale yellow solid	51.96 (52.07)	6.98 (7.04)	29.28 (29.33)	410 (415)
(4) C ₁₆ H ₂₅ SbO ₃	Pale yellow solid	49.58 (49.64)	6.48 (6.51)	31.40 (31.45)	380 (387)
(5) C ₂₀ H ₃₃ SbO ₃	Pale yellow solid	54.15 (54.20)	7.45 (7.50)	27.40 (27.47)	440 (443)

organic solvents (e.g. benzene, toluene, dichloromethane, etc.) and depict monomeric nature (ebullioscopically) in benzene solution.

Spectroscopic studies :

The IR and ¹H NMR assignments¹¹⁻¹⁴ (Table 2) have been made on the basis of published data about glycols, substituted phenols, and mixed-ligand derivatives of elements.

(a) IR spectra : Derivatives (1)-(5) exhibit medium to strong absorptions in the region 1220-1280 cm⁻¹, due to ν(C-O) of aryloxy moiety. An increase of ~15 cm⁻¹ in the ν(C-O) of aryloxy group, supports O-bonded

Table 2. Salient IR (cm⁻¹) and ¹H NMR (δ, ppm) spectral data for antimony(III) glycolate-aryloxy derivatives (1)-(5)

(1)	IR : 1073m ν(C-O) glycolate, 1220s ν(C-O) aryloxy, 852m ν(C-C) glycolate, 576w ν(Sb-O), 750s (ring pulsation), 458w (ring vibration). ¹ H NMR : 1.57 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.18 (6H, s, CMe ₂), 1.22 (3H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe), 4.45 (1H, br, CHMe) glycolate; 2.28 (6H, s, Me ₂ -2,6), 6.81-7.35 (3H, m, Ar-H) aryloxy.
(2)	IR : 1073m ν(C-O) glycolate, 1279s ν(C-O) aryloxy, 867s ν(C-C), 720m (ring pulsation), 577s ν(Sb-O), 473m (ring vibration). ¹ H NMR : 1.63 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.29 (6H, s, CMe ₂), 1.25 (3H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe), 4.72 (1H, br, CHMe) glycolate; 2.21 (3H, s, Me-5), 1.18 (6H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe ₂), 3.29 (1H, sept, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe ₂), 6.68-7.44 (3H, m, Ar-H) aryloxy.
(3)	IR : 1088s ν(C-O) glycolate, 1250m ν(C-O) aryloxy, 823s ν(C-C), 706m (ring pulsation), 547s ν(Sb-O), 466s (ring vibration). ¹ H NMR : 1.30 (3H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe), 1.47 (2H, m, CH ₂), 2.28 (6H, s, CMe ₂), 4.82 (1H, br, CHMe) glycolate; 1.17 (12H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe ₂), 3.34 (2H, sept, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe ₂), 6.78-7.45 (3H, m, Ar-H) aryloxy.
(4)	IR : 1044s ν(C-O) glycolate, 1227s ν(C-O) aryloxy, 868m ν(C-C), 757s (ring pulsation), 582m ν(Sb-O), 451s (ring vibration). ¹ H NMR : 1.36 (12H, s, CMe ₂), 1.48 (4H, m, CH ₂) glycolate; 2.37 (6H, s, Me ₂ -2,6), 6.75-7.45 (3H, m, Ar-H) aryloxy.
(5)	IR : 1088s ν(C-O) glycolate, 1220m ν(C-O) aryloxy, 867s ν(C-C), 720w (ring pulsation), 548s ν(Sb-O), 466m (ring vibration). ¹ H NMR : 1.35 (12H, s, CMe ₂), 1.54 (4H, m, CH ₂) glycolate; 1.22 (12H, d, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe ₂), 3.45 (2H, sept, J 6.2 Hz, CHMe ₂), 6.91-7.44 (3H, m, Ar-H) aryloxy.

IR : Abbreviations : s = strong, m = medium, w = weak.

¹H NMR : Abbreviations : s = singlet, d = doublet, m = multiplet, sept = septet, br = broad.

aryloxo group to antimony(III). The absorptions due to $\nu(\text{Sb-O})$ appear in the region $545\text{--}585\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Absorptions observed in the regions $700\text{--}760\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $450\text{--}475\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are due to ring pulsation and ring vibrations, respectively.

(b) $^1\text{H NMR spectra}$: The signal due to OH group of the substituted phenols in the region $\delta\ 4.70\text{--}4.90$ is absent in derivatives (1)–(5), supporting the metallation of the phenolic OH group proton and formation of Sb-OAr bond. All these derivatives show (Table 2) multiplets due to aromatic ring protons in the region $\delta\ 6.70\text{--}7.50$. Signals characteristic of a glycolate group appear in the regions : $\delta\ 1.20\text{--}1.30$ (d, $J\ 6.2\ \text{Hz}$, CHMe), $1.40\text{--}1.70$ (br, CH_2), $2.10\text{--}2.30$ (s, CMe₂), $4.40\text{--}4.90$ (m, CHMe). The substituents present on an aryloxo group show signals for derivatives : (1) at $\delta\ 2.28$ (s, Me₂-2,6); (2) at $\delta\ 1.18$ (d, $J\ 6.2\ \text{Hz}$, CHMe₂), 2.21 (s, Me-5), 3.29 (sept, $J\ 6.2\ \text{Hz}$, CHMe₂); (3) at $\delta\ 1.17$ (d, $J\ 6.2\ \text{Hz}$, CHMe₂), 3.34 (sept, $J\ 6.2\ \text{Hz}$, CHMe₂); (4) at $\delta\ 2.37$ (s, Me₂-2,6); (5) at $\delta\ 1.22$ (d, $J\ 6.2\ \text{Hz}$, CHMe₂), 3.45 (sept, $J\ 6.2\ \text{Hz}$, CHMe₂).

The aforementioned findings along with the data available for mixed-ligand derivatives of arsenic(III)^{13a} and antimony(III)¹² in the literature, tend to favour the structure shown below for compounds (1)–(5) :

where $G = \text{CHMeCH}_2\text{CMe}_2$ and $\text{CMe}_2(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CMe}_2$;
 $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Me}_2\text{-}2,6$, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}_2\text{-}2,6$ and $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}^i\text{-}2\text{-Me-}5$

Experimental

All preparations and manipulations were performed under strictly moisture-free conditions as already described in some of our earlier publications^{10–12}. Benzene and *n*-hexane were dried and purified under anhydrous conditions by refluxing over Na/benzophenone, followed by distillation prior to use. Dichloromethane was dried by refluxing over P₂O₅, followed by distillation (b.p. $39\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$).

2-Methylpentane-2,4-diol (b.p. $197\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/756\ \text{mm}$) (BDH) and 2,5-dimethylhexane-2,5-diol (b.p. $214\text{ }^\circ\text{C}/756\ \text{mm}$) (Aldrich) were distilled prior to use. Sb(OPr^{*i*})₃ was prepared by the literature method^{10,14b}. The precu-

ror derivatives, $\overline{\text{OGOSbOPr}}^i$ ($G = \text{CHMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2$ and $\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2$) were prepared according to the procedure described in the literature^{10,11}. Isopropyl alcohol in the azeotrope was estimated oxidimetrically¹⁵ using $1\ N\ \text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$ solution in $12.5\% \text{ H}_2\text{SO}_4$. Antimony was determined volumetrically¹⁶.

IR ($4000\text{--}200\ \text{cm}^{-1}$) spectra were recorded as Nujol mulls on a Nicolet Magna 550 spectrophotometer using CsI optics. $^1\text{H NMR}$ ($89.55\ \text{MHz}$, CDCl_3) were recorded on a JEOL FX-90Q spectrometer using TMS (tetramethylsilane) as an internal reference. C, H analyses were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Series II CHNS/O analyzer-2400. Molecular weights were determined (on a Gallenkamp ebulliometer using thermister sensing device) ebullioscopically in benzene.

Synthesis of antimony(III) glycoxide-aryloxides (1)–(5) :

These derivatives have been prepared by two routes : (i) reactions of $\overline{\text{OGOSbOPr}}^i$ with appropriate substituted phenols and (ii) *in situ* equimolar reaction of Sb(OPr^{*i*})₃ with a glycol and a substituted phenol, the former route was used for the synthesis of all the five compounds, whereas the latter route was used to prepare $\overline{\text{OCMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{OSbOC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Me}_2\text{-}2,6$.

Due to similarity in the preparative procedures, synthetic details of only one derivative for each route are described below :

(i) $\overline{\text{OCHMeCH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{OSbOC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}_2\text{-}2,6}$ (3) :

To a benzene (40 ml) solution of $\overline{\text{OCHMeCH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{OSbOPr}}^i$ (1.54 g, 5.20 mmol) was added $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}_2\text{-}2,6$ (0.928 g, 5.20 mmol) dissolved in benzene (20 ml), and the reaction mixture was refluxed over a period of $\sim 10\ \text{h}$, during which time the liberated isopropyl alcohol was continuously fractionated out azeotropically and estimated periodically to check completion of the reaction. When the azeotrope showed negligible presence of an oxidisable material, the refluxing was stopped and the solution was allowed to cool to room temperature. Removal of the volatile components from the solution under reduced pressure afforded a white solid product (2.10 g, 92%), which was recrystallized in analytically pure state (1.80 g, 83.3%) from a 2 : 1 mixture of *n*-hexane and CH_2Cl_2 at $-20\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Using a procedure similar to that employed for (3), the other derivatives (1), (2), (4) and (5) were also pre-

pared. The amount of reactants actually used are shown in square brackets against each compound listed below :

(1) : $\text{OCHMeCH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{OSbOPr}^i$ [0.80 g, 2.69 mmol] and $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Me}_2\text{-2,6}$ [0.33 g, 2.69 mmol]. Yield 0.94 g (90%). Isopropyl alcohol in the azeotrope (Calcd. 0.162 g, Found 0.16 g).

(2) : $\text{OCHMeCH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{OSbOPr}^i$ [2.21 g, 7.44 mmol] and $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}^i\text{-2-Me-5}$ [1.11 g, 7.44 mmol]. Yield 2.80 g (91 %). Isopropyl alcohol in the azeotrope (Calcd. 0.447 g, Found 0.44 g).

(4) : $\text{OCMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{OSbOPr}^i$ [1.78 g, 5.47 mmol] and $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Me}_2\text{-2,6}$ [0.669 g, 5.47 mmol]. Yield 1.98 g (94%). Isopropyl alcohol in the azeotrope (Calcd. 0.329 g, Found 0.32 g).

(5) : $\text{OCMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{OSbOPr}^i$ [0.826 g, 2.54 mmol] and $\text{HOC}_6\text{H}_3\text{Pr}^i\text{-2,6}$ [0.453 g, 2.54 mmol]. Yield 1.18 g (97%). Isopropyl alcohol in the azeotrope (Calcd. 0.152 g, Found 0.15 g).

Analytical details and some physical properties of all the new derivatives (1)-(5) are summarized in Table 1.

(ii) *Preparation of (1) by an alternative route :*

The benzene (80 ml) solution containing equimolar amounts of $\text{Sb}(\text{OPr}^i)_3$ (1.5 g, 5.02 mmol), 2-methyl-2,4-pentanediol (0.58 g, 4.99 mmol) and 2,6-dimethyl phenol (0.61 g, 4.99 mmol) was refluxed for ~24 h, during which time the liberated isopropyl alcohol was continuously fractionated out and determined periodically to monitor the progress and completion of the reaction. When azeotrope collected showed negligible presence of Pr^iOH , the refluxing was stopped and solution was allowed to cool to room temperature. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure to afford white solid, which was recrystallized from a 2 : 1 mixture of *n*-hexane-dichloromethane at -20°C to give 1.58 g of the desired product. Yield 88% (Found : C, 46.76; H, 5.82; Sb, 33.88. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{21}\text{SbO}_3$: C, 46.83; H, 5.81; Sb, 33.91%).

Conclusion

Convenient and quantitative syntheses of five glycolate-aryloxide derivatives of antimony(III), which are hydrocarbon soluble and monomeric, are reported for the first time.

Acknowledgement

We thank the UGC, New Delhi for financial support. Our sincere thanks are to the Head, Department of Chem-

istry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, for providing research facilities.

References

- (a) K. C. Malhotra and R. L. Martin, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1982, **239**, 159; (b) M. H. Chisholm and I. P. Rothwell, in "Comprehensive Coordination Chemistry", eds. G. Wilkinson, R. D. Gillard and J. A. Me Cleverty, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1987, Vol. 2, Chap. 15.3; (c) H. E. Bryndza and W. Tam, *Chem. Rev.*, 1988, **88**, 1163; (d) K. G. Caulton and L. G. Hubert-Pfalzgraf, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 969; (e) W. G. Vander Sluys and A. P. Sattelberger, *Chem. Rev.*, 1990, **90**, 1027; (f) R. C. Mehrotra, A. Singh and U. M. Tripathi, *Chem. Rev.*, 1991, **91**, 1287; (g) M. D. Healy, M. B. Power and A. R. Barron, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **130**, 63; (h) C. J. Carmalt and S. J. King, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2006, **250**, 687; (i) T. J. Boyle and L. A. M. Ottley, *Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **108**, 1896.
- D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra, I. P. Rothwell and A. Singh, "Alkoxo and Aryloxo Derivatives of Metals", Academic Press, London, 2001.
- L. Que, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1983, **50**, 73.
- R. C. Mehrotra and A. Singh, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1997, **46**, 239.
- A. Singh and R. C. Mehrotra, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **248**, 101.
- H. Fleischer, H. Bayram, S. Elzner and N. W. Mitzel, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2001, 373.
- G. A. Horley, M. F. Mahon, K. C. Molloy and M. M. Venter, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2002, **41**, 1652.
- U. Ensinger, W. Schwarz, B. Schrutz, K. Sommer and A. Z. Schmidt, *Anorg. Allg. Chem.*, 1987, **544**, 181.
- S. M. Biros, B. M. Bridgewater, A. V-Estrada, J. M. Tanski and G. Parkin, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2002, **41**, 4051.
- R. C. Mehrotra and D. D. Bhatnagar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 327.
- S. Goyal and A. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2001, **40**, 1302.
- T. Athar, R. Bohra and R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 189.
- (a) S. Goyal and A. Singh, *Synth. React. Inorg Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1319; (b) S. Goyal and A. Singh, *Phosphorus, Sulfur and Silicon*, 2003, **1**, 178; (c) S. Goyal, PhD Thesis, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur, India, 2003.
- (a) S. Goyal and A. Singh, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1433; (b) T. B. Brill and N. C. Campbell, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, **12**, 1884.
- (a) C. Adams and J. R. Nichollas, *Analyst*, 1929, **50**, 2; (b) R. C. Mehrotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 585.
- A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 5th ed., Longmans, London, 1978.